

EDUCATION ASSOCIATED WITH MEDICAL ENGLISH

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Abstract. The English language, due to its role in the world today, has become the cornerstone of higher education development. One’s ability to speak specific English to his domain is a good asset required by job market and scientific research. Knowledge of English language enables us to participate in various international medical conferences, after which we can cooperate with international colleagues in the field of health care.

Key words: english for medicine, approach, specialty, health schools, medical tourism, make diagnoses, volunteer.

Аннотация. Английский язык, благодаря своей роли в современном мире, стал краеугольным камнем в развитии высшего образования. Способность человека говорить на английском языке, соответствующем его предмету, является хорошим активом, необходимым для рынка труда и научных исследований. Знание английского языка позволяет нам участвовать в различных международных медицинских конференциях, после чего мы можем сотрудничать с международными коллегами в сфере здравоохранения.

Ключевые слова: английский для медиков, подход, специальность, школы здоровья, туризм, поставить диагноз, волонтер.

Annotatsiya. Ingliz tili bugungi kunda dunyoda tutgan o’rni tufayli oliy ta’lim rivojining poydevoriga aylandi. Biror kishining o’z domenida o’ziga xos ingliz tilida gaplasha olish qobiliyati mehnat bozori va ilmiy tadqiqotlar talab qiladigan yaxshi aktivdir. Ingliz tilini bilish til bizga turli xalqaro tibbiy konferensiyalarda qatnashish imkonini beradi, shundan so’ng biz sog’liqni saqlash sohasida xalqaro hamkasblar bilan hamkorlik qilishimiz mumkin.

Kalit so`zlar: tibbiyot yo’nalishi uchun ingliz tili, yondashuv, mutaxassislik, sog’liqni saqlash maktablari, turizm, tashxis qo’yish, ko’ngilli.

Introduction. Nowadays, many medical students choose to learn special English on their own. But there is also a second method of learning with a specialist. If you have a language base and do not want to save money to study with a specialist, self-study seems like a good choice. However, do not naively assume that you can make any progress in modern medicine by studying less than twice a week.

Language is a tool of communication. It designs particularly the manner of expressing ideas and feeling either through speech or written, even through gestures. English in Benin environment is a foreign language, and it is one of the most essential international languages for communication. It is the language of communication and business, worldwide. It is used in many domains and enterprises where it is used as a medium of exchange. English is very important in getting a better job and in social interaction with people around the world

In medical schools, students, after years of study, still feel important difficulty in using specific English. They are not able to communicate appropriately by using terminologies of their specialty whereas medical science is a universal science which uses English a lot as a medium of communication and treatment. Also, drugs, vaccines, surgical materials and other medical products' labels are always or partly in English.

Some categories or learners use translators softwares to face their scientific understand problems, but later on there will happen a context in which they are confronted to incorrectness of retrieval documents. As the wants or needs, and even it is difficult to arrange schedules between studying and learning English program for specificity, learners must manage to continue reading English without getting into trouble with their option in higher education like in medical schools.

For those with a medical background, specializing in Medical English is a great way to up their earning power overseas and online! Let me clarify what I mean when I say “medical background”. I’m not just speaking of medical doctors and nurses here. If you’ve worked in the pharmaceutical industry, medical transcription, worked as an EMT, First Responder, in the dental field, or even veterinary medicine, you have a certain vocabulary that professionals will pay for.

There is a growing market for what is known as “medical tourism” around the world. As the cost of medical care rises in developed countries, making it more difficult for residents of those countries to afford medical care, many are getting their procedures performed in foreign countries. This has created an increasing demand for English teachers with a medical background because they have the technical vocabulary to go along with their native English abilities. But, teaching medical English sometimes goes beyond just medical terminology and English ability.

As an English teacher working with professionals in the medical community, you may find yourself teaching communication techniques with specific types of patients. Treating children requires a distinct approach than treating adults, and treating elderly patients can require even different communication.

You may even teach how communication works between different medical professionals. Certainly, as a medical professional, you communicate differently with a colleague you’ve worked with for years than you do with a highly-respected, well-known doctor presenting at a medical conference, someone you’ve never met before.

Medical English also often involves helping students use the right vocabulary to recognize health problems, make diagnoses, give proper treatments, and avoid errors while working with English speaking patients. Medical English students want to know how to (in English):

- Ask clear questions;
- Elicit information needed from patients;
- Report observations and reactions;
- Give clear instructions and explanations to clients and their families as well co-workers;
- Read & write.

If you're a medical professional and would like to leverage both your English skills and your medical background, take some time to explore opportunities in your desired city or country. Do some research in that area. Look into who might be in need of your services. Consider:

Hospitals	Pharmacists
Clinics	Medical Sales staff
Doctor's offices	Veterinarians
Dentists	Emergency caregivers
Bodyworkers	Personal/home
Nutrition&Fitness professionals	health workers
	Medical Students

There are a variety of ways you can market yourself to your potential clients/students. You could use any one of these methods to help people understand what you have to offer to help them improve their English proficiency:

Business Cards	Free classes
Flyers	Visiting lecturer
Administrator visits	Volunteer

As you well know, medical professionals are busy people. They might not have a lot of time to dedicate to the process of improving their English. So, you'll want to have a variety of offerings to suit the needs of various types of students.

Individual tutoring	Longer (1- to 2-week) intensive training
Small group sessions	Lecture series
Weekend "office hours"	Online classes

There are also other reasons for learning English. The knowledge of English helps in finding a common language with sophisticated equipment that is imported from other countries, which is not unimportant for a doctor. A doctor who speaks a

foreign language, more precisely English, is always highly valued in any company, in any profession.

Conclusion: As a medical professional, you’ve dedicated your life to service. Just because you’re transitioning out of the way you’ve always helped others, doesn’t mean that you can no longer contribute using your vast medical experience. It just may take looking at it differently and applying it in a new way, but you’ll continue making a positive impact on the world by helping other medical professionals improve their careers and level of treatment. Take some time to look into medical opportunities that suit your future live abroad or travel lifestyle!

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